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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A SAR WIND EMULATOR

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ESA SAR OCEAN WIND, WAVES AND CURRENTS

by

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Introduction

It is realised that the spatial coverage and irregular revisit time of SAR sensors is not adequate for direct use of SAR-retrieved wind in operational weather forecasting or for assimilation into numerical forecast models. Therefore a new way is sought to take benefit from the obvious strength of SAR for high resolution wind speed retrieval. The approach investigated in this study is to develop a transfer function which can prescribe (emulate) a high resolution wind field from a given lower resolution weather forecast model field. Such a transfer function (or emulator) can be trained to “learn” the micrometeorological conditions of specific regions by co-locating a large historical dataset of model and SAR derived wind fields. Once developed, this emulator can then be used in real time, or even forecast situation, to emulate the high resolution wind fields from the coarse model output, without the need for additional real time SAR data. The potential gain of such an emulator is largest in coastal regions with complex topography, where variations in wind speed and direction may be large on a fine scale. In this study, two regions with complex fjord-topography along the Norwegian coast are selected as study areas.

Wind retrieval from Envisat ASAR

Envisat ASAR images are read and calibrated with Matlab software developed at NERSC. The backscatter images are downsampled from a pixel size of 75 metres to about 535 metres with an anti-aliasing lowpass filter (“resample” function in Matlab with N=10) to reduce noise, speckle and data volume. From these “quicklooks”, wind speed is calculated in this study with the CMOD4 algorithm (Stoffelen et al., 1997), where the auxiliary wind direction is taken from the NCEP Global Forecast System (GFS). The GFS model is initialised every 6 hours, and provides forecast output for every 3 hours. The 0 hour (initialization) or 3 hour forecast field, whichever is closest in time to the SAR image, is used for the SAR wind inversion. The pixel size of NCEP GFS is 0.5 degrees, and the wind direction is interpolated (component by component) to the ASAR grid with linear interpolation before the SAR wind retrieval.

Mean Envisat ASAR wind field maps

The two study areas along the Norwegian coast are shown in Figure 1. Wind speed is calculated from all available Envisat ASAR Wide Swath Mode images as described in the last section, and interpolated onto regular grids converting the study areas at a resolution of about

500 metres. The corresponding NCEP GFS model wind speed and direction, which is used as auxiliary data for the SAR wind retrieval, is interpolated to the same grids.

Figure 1: The red rectangles define the two study areas at the western (59.5-63.75N, 2-7.5E) and northern (70-73N, 19-31E) coast of Norway. The highest mountains in southern Norway (white colour) are nearly 2500 metres.

Both regions have complex coastlines and topography, and are therefore very challenging for numerical weather forecast models. Expectedly, the wind patterns in such regions are variable on a small scale and highly dependent on the synoptic situation (general wind direction, type of flow, stability etc). The question to be investigated in this study is whether this small scale wind variability, as imaged with SAR, can be directly linked to the synoptic flow, as described by a forecast model.

Four full years of Envisat ASAR data, from May 2005 to May 2009, have been provided by ESA. NCEP GFS model data are only available at NERSC since June 2006, for SAR images before this date NCEP/NCAR reanalysis data at a coarser grid (about 1.8 degree pixel size) available every 6 hours is used instead.

The mean ASAR and NCEP wind speed for the two regions are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, and the number of ASAR images used for the calculations is shown in Figure 4. About 10% of the SAR scenes have been manually discarded before averaging due to obviously wrong wind direction and consequently wrong wind speed, mainly cases with sharp wind fronts.

Figure 2: Mean wind speed from Envisat ASAR (top) and NCEP GFS model (bottom) for the region in Northern Norway. Wind measurement stations used for validation are indicated on the lower figure.

Figure 3: Mean wind speed from Envisat ASAR (top) and NCEP GFS model (bottom) for the region in South-Western Norway. Wind measurement stations used for validation are indicated on the lower figure.

Figure 4: The number of Envisat ASAR images covering the two study regions.

Both the SAR and model averaged wind fields are quite smooth, with homogeneous wind speed offshore, and lower wind speeds closer to the coast and in the fjords. However, the SAR mean wind shows some more variability than NCEP GFS model inside the fjords.

More interesting than the overall mean wind speed is when the composites are made separately for different model wind directions, as seen in Figure 5 and Figure 6. Here it is seen that some parts inside and directly outside of the fjords have much higher mean wind speed for some wind directions than others, and that some areas are in a wind shadow with lower wind speeds for some wind directions. Whereas much of the patterns look reasonable and could have been qualitatively anticipated, some surprising features are also observed where the wind speed is actually higher for the model wind direction perpendicular to the fjord than along the fjord. This reflects that the real wind direction and speed changes very rapidly within such complex topography. The composite wind speed maps have been shown to local operational weather forecasters, who find the results very interesting. Since there are few wind measurements in the region, the forecasters can not confirm the results, but with their long term experience the wind patterns are found reasonable, though partly surprising.

Figure 5: Mean wind fields for the region in Northern Norway calculated separately for only situations where the interpolated NCEP wind direction at each pixel is within the 30 degree angular bin as indicated by the two white arrows.

Figure 6: Same as Figure 5, but for the region in South-Western Norway.

Validation of NCEP and SAR winds versus *in situ* observations

The NCEP GFS model and SAR derived wind speeds are here compared to *in situ* measurements from the nine measurement stations listed in Table 1. All stations except the two buoys are synoptic (SYNOP) weather stations operated by the Norwegian met office. The data from these stations are available from <http://eklima.met.no>. The buoy at Nordkyn is operated by the Norwegian Coastal Administration (Kystverket), and data are available from http://www.oceanor.com/Barents_Sea/. The buoy at Rosendal in Hardangerfjord is operated by the Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, and data are available from <http://talos.nodc.no:8080/observasjonsboye/>. Data from the latter buoy is provided every 10 minutes, but are averaged over one hour for the validation. Both buoys are measuring at 3 metre height, but wind speeds are adjusted to 10 metre height by the data providers. One station is on the "Troll" oil platform in the North Sea, while the remaining 6 stations are located on islands on the coastline, with heights above sea level between 6 and 38 metres. It must be kept in mind that the wind measurements over land may be influenced by the local terrain, and may be different from the wind over water nearby, as retrieved with SAR.

Table 1: Nine wind measurements stations along the Norwegian coast used for validation of the NCEP, SAR and emulated winds.

Station	Latitude	Longitude	Height above sea level [m]
Fedje	60.78	4.72	19
Ona	62.86	6.54	13
Svinøy	62.32	5.27	38
Troll	60.60	3.70	Oil platform
Hasvik	70.49	22.15	6
Fruholmen	71.09	24.00	13
Slettnes	71.08	28.22	8
Nordkyn	71.58	28.50	Buoy
Rosendal	59.99	5.92	Buoy

For comparison with the SAR derived wind, the SAR pixels have been shifted manually a few kilometers to avoid contamination from land on the backscatter values, as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Zoom in around the 9 wind measurement stations used for validation. The white asterisks mark the location of the measurement station, according to given coordinates. Black areas is a land mask from the GTOPO30 dataset, at a resolution of about 1 km. The coloured background is the mean SAR/CMOD4 wind speed, with the same colourmap as in Figure 6. Reddish-colors close to land areas indicate very high mean wind speed, but are artifacts from land contamination due to incomplete coverage of the GTOPO30 dataset, or due to dislocation or layover effects of the SAR images. The red asterisks mark the locations of the SAR pixels which are used for comparison with the *in situ* measurements (and for the emulator development); these locations have been shifted manually to avoid land contamination, but to stay as close to the *in situ* station as possible. The buoy positions at Nordkyn and Rosendal have not been shifted.

The comparison of NCEP and SAR wind speeds with the *in situ* wind speed measurements is shown in Table 2. The root mean square error is 3.0 m/s for both the NCEP GFS model and for the SAR derived wind speed. This accuracy for SAR winds is lower than the typical values of 1.5-2 m/s reported by other studies, but validation in the coastal zone with complex topography is more challenging than with offshore buoys normally used. The highest accuracy for both the model and the SAR derived wind is found with the offshore station at “Troll”, with RMSE of 2.3-2.5 m/s. As a sensitivity test, wind was also calculated from the SAR images with the wind direction taken from the *in situ* measurements. The improvement compared to the measured wind speeds was very slight, indicating that wrong wind direction for the CMOD-inversion is not an important error source in general, although a parallel study has shown that a Bayesian approach utilizing the Doppler velocity may improve significantly the wind for cases with strong wind gradients. It is noticeable that the bias of the NCEP and SAR winds always have the same sign compared with the *in situ* measurements, and have often similar magnitude. This suggests that each measurement station has its own characteristics, probably due to local terrain effects or improper calibration, and there seem to be more consistency between the mean NCEP and SAR derived winds. The CMOD-IFR2 algorithm (Quilfen et al., 1998) was also tested as an alternative to CMOD4, but the difference of the validation was negligible. Wind from the Hirlam model at 10 km resolution was also tested both directly versus the *in situ* measurements, and for providing wind direction for the SAR wind inversion. Despite the improved spatial resolution, no improvement was found when comparing with the *in situ* measurements. Since Hirlam data was also available only for one year, NCEP GFS wind has been used throughout this study.

Table 2: Comparison of NCEP and SAR derived wind speed with *in situ* measurements from the nine stations listed in Table 1. <speed> means average wind speed over the given number of observations, spread between May 2005 and May 2009. The *in situ* and NCEP time closest to a given SAR image is used for the comparison. "corr" means correlation coefficient; "bias" is model or SAR wind speed minus *in situ* wind, and "rmse" is the root mean square error. Comparison with SAR wind speed is shown both with wind direction taken from the NCEP model, and when using the *in situ* wind direction as input to the SAR wind retrieval algorithm (CMOD4).

<i>In situ</i>			NCEP				CMOD4/NCEP direction				CMOD4/obs. direction			
Station	#obs	<speed>	<speed>	corr	bias	rmse	<speed>	corr	bias	rmse	<speed>	corr	bias	rmse
Fedje	594	7.6	6.8	0.80	-0.8	2.7	6.7	0.73	-1.0	3.1	6.3	0.75	-1.2	3.0
Ona	626	7.3	6.9	0.68	-0.4	3.5	6.2	0.74	-1.1	3.3	6.1	0.72	-1.2	3.4
Svinøy	675	8.3	7.3	0.72	-1.0	3.5	7.0	0.79	-1.3	3.2	6.8	0.82	-1.6	3.2
Troll	549	8.2	8.4	0.87	0.2	2.3	8.2	0.84	0.0	2.5	8.2	0.84	0.1	2.5
Hasvik	661	5.5	6.5	0.71	1.0	2.8	6.8	0.75	1.3	3.0	6.1	0.76	0.6	2.5
Fruholmen	690	8.3	7.6	0.80	-0.7	2.9	7.5	0.80	-0.8	2.9	7.4	0.82	-0.9	2.8
Slettnes	559	7.2	7.7	0.73	0.5	2.9	7.5	0.71	0.3	3.2	7.4	0.73	0.3	3.0
Nordkyn	63	7.1	8.3	0.81	1.2	2.5	8.5	0.70	1.5	3.3	9.0	0.74	2.0	3.4
Rosendal	189	3.1	4.4	0.79	1.4	2.3	3.9	0.69	0.9	2.3	3.8	0.60	0.7	2.6
Overall	4606	7.3	7.2	0.76	-0.1	3.0	7.0	0.75	-0.3	3.0	6.8	0.77	-0.5	2.9

Development of high resolution transfer functions (wind emulators)

Two different approaches are tested here for the transfer functions to relate the high resolution wind variations as seen with SAR to the coarser resolution wind information as provided by the NCEP GFS model. The first approach is to train a neural network to relate the SAR wind speed at any pixel to the model wind speed and direction interpolated to the same pixel. Such a function can be expressed by:

$$W_{i,j} = F_{i,j}(NCEP_windspeed_{interpolated}, NCEP_winddirection_{interpolated})$$

where i,j indicates spatial position of the high resolution grid, and $W_{i,j}$ is the output (emulated) wind speed at this position. One function (neural network) like this has been trained for the co-located dataset of SAR and NCEP GFS model winds for each of the *in situ* measurement stations listed in Table 1 and shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Note that the *in situ* observations are here not used for the development of the emulators, only for validating the performance. The network has in this study been trained using the Neural Network Toolbox available for Matlab (www.mathworks.com/products/neuralnet/). The default network is trained with two input neurons, for a maximum of 500 epochs and with a learning rate of 0.05 and a performance goal of 0.000001. Several variations and combinations of these variables were tested, but the above configuration gave best results for the validation to be shown later.

The second, and very simple, approach is to use the same co-located dataset to quantify the bias between the SAR-retrieved and modeled wind speed, and then to correct for this bias in the real time situation when SAR wind is not available. The bias correction for the pixel (i,j) can be expressed by:

$$B_{i,j} = \langle SAR_wind_{i,j} - NCEP_windspeed_{interpolated} \rangle$$

where the brackets denote averaging over the whole training dataset. In a real time situation, the high resolution bias-corrected wind field is then given by:

$$W_{i,j} = NCEP_windspeed_{interpolated} + B_{i,j}$$

In this study several variations of the bias correction is tested:

- bias is averaged over all situations, and is hence a constant value for a given pixel.
- bias is calculated separately for the model wind direction within discrete angular bins
- bias is calculated separately for the model wind speed within discrete angular bins
- a combination of the two above, where bias is calculated for model wind speed and directions within 2D bins (boxes)

The wind direction bins used here have a width of 30 degrees (See Figure 10), and the wind speed bins are 5 m/s (0, 5, 10, 15, ... m/s). Several different sizes of the angular bins (45, 60, 90 and 180 degrees) and the wind speed bins (2 and 10 m/s steps) were also tested, but this gave no improvement for the validation to be shown below. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the constant bias, and Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the bias calculated separately for model wind direction within the angular bins of 30 degrees.

Figure 8: Average SAR/CMOD4 minus NCEP wind speed for the region in Northern Norway.

Figure 9: Average SAR/CMOD4 minus NCEP wind speed for the region in South-Western Norway. Note that some of the high positive bias values in the most narrow fjords are clearly due to land contamination due to layover effects from the steep terrain, or mis-location of some of the SAR images. This effect is most noticeable for fjords aligned north-south, since the SAR look direction is mainly along the east-west direction. The points with positive values in the North Sea are artifacts due to strong backscatter from oil platforms.

Figure 10: Mean SAR/CMOD4 wind speed minus NCEP GFS model wind speed for the region in Northern Norway, calculated separately for the NCEP wind direction within the angular bins as indicated by the two white arrows.

An example of the application of the wind direction dependent bias corrector (emulator) is seen in Figure 12. Note that no SAR image available concurrently in space and time is needed for this case; the high resolution on the right figure is added solely based on information stored in the emulator which is trained on historical SAR imagery. Therefore the model field may be a long term forecast, just as well as a nowcast or model initialization wind field.

Figure 11: Same as Figure 10, but for the region in South-Western Norway.

Figure 12: An example of practical use of a high resolution transfer function (wind emulator). The left figure shows an original NCEP model speed field, and the middle figure shows the same field smoothed with linear interpolation. The right wind speed map is obtained after application of the transfer function which corrects for SAR-NCEP bias constant for NCEP wind direction within angular bins of 30 degrees (Figure 11). Colormap is the same as in Figure 6.

Validation of the wind emulators

The performance of the wind emulators described in the previous section is here tested versus an independent dataset consisting of all co-locations of *in situ* measurements and NCEP GFS model fields from 2007 and 2008. The development dataset (Table 2) consists of all situations where SAR data is available, whereas for the larger validation dataset (Table 3) no SAR data is available (Remind that the point of the wind emulator is to provide high resolution wind speed for the general case (including the future/forecast) when only model wind and no SAR data is available.).

For the validation dataset shown in Table 3, the overall bias (model minus observation) and root mean square error of the NCEP GFS model are 0.2 and 2.5 m/s respectively. None of the tested emulators are seen to be able to improve the coarse model in the overall case. One notable exception is the station at Hasvik, where the emulators which are function of wind speed (with or without wind direction) show some slight improvement. As seen in Figure 2, this station is also one of the few which are located where the SAR wind composite shows largest spatial gradient in wind speed.

The simplest of the emulators, the correction of an overall constant bias, performs best of the emulators in general; the overall bias is reduced from 0.2 to 0.1 m/s compared to the original NCEP GFS model output, but the rmse is increased from 2.5 to 2.6 m/s. The fact that the wind emulators which use separate bias for bins of model wind speed and direction show worse results than the constant bias/emulator is at first a bit surprising. However, it is clear that the bias calculated separately for 12 bins (Figure 10 and Figure 11) is less spatially coherent than the overall bias which is constant for each pixel (Figure 8 and Figure 9). The plausible explanation is that there are too few scenes with wind speed within a certain bin to make a robust average, and hence individual and unrepresentative SAR scenes may have a large influence. This will be further discussed in the next section.

An important question arising is how much of the deviations are due to imperfect SAR wind retrieval (i.e. artifacts caused by non-wind features, wrong auxiliary wind direction, instrument calibration etc.), and how much is due to shortcomings of the proposed emulator models, or method in general. To eliminate the uncertainty due to imperfect SAR wind retrieval, and also due to different location of the closest usable SAR pixel and the *in situ* station, a test is performed where the emulators are trained to predict directly the *in situ* measurements from the coarser model wind. When these emulators are validated against the same *in situ* measurement stations (but of course with an independent set of measurements), the remaining error could be attributed to the chosen emulator methods. As seen in Table 4, the bias is now significantly reduced for each single station, with a few exceptions which likely are due to too few scenes within certain wind speed/direction bins. This suggests that most of the bias of the SAR-emulators (Table 3) is from either 1) the SAR wind retrieval method, 2) the different location of the SAR wind pixel over water and the *in situ* station, or 3) imperfect calibration or local characteristics of the *in situ* wind measurement station. The latter explanation is supported by the fact that Table 2 shows that the bias of the NCEP and SAR-retrieved wind versus *in situ* measurements always have the same sign and similar magnitude for each of the stations. Hence, the local characteristics of each *in situ* wind measurement station seem to dominate over the relatively small wind speed corrections

suggested by the SAR wind emulator. Based on this, the following validation exercise for the SAR wind emulator could be suggested: two or three buoys could be deployed at the same location for some weeks, for precise intercalibration. One or two of the buoys could then be moved to location(s) nearby where the SAR predicts higher or lower winds. The preceding intercalibration should then remove the bias among the buoys, and ensure that they are able to discriminate the spatial wind speed variations suggested by the SAR.

Although the emulators trained directly on the *in situ* stations were able to reduce the bias significantly (Table 4), the root mean square errors are generally not reduced very much compared to the SAR emulators (Table 3). This indicated that a substantial part of the variability is an inherent characteristic of the real wind, at least at these locations close to complex terrain. All the *in situ* wind measurements have been averaged over one hour, both for the training and validation datasets. However, for the buoy at Rosendal averaged wind is available also every 10 minutes. Figure 13 shows a (not untypical) time series of the 10 minute wind speed during a day. Very strong changes in wind speed of more than 3 m/s are seen within less than half an hour. This strong variability indicates that the measured wind speed, even when averaged over one hour, will be very sensitive to a small shift of the timing. The data in Table 4 indicates that an rmse of about 2 m/s seems to be a lower limit for the accuracy possible with any model or wind emulator stations in the fjords, whereas an rmse of 1.6 m/s is achievable for the offshore station Troll.

Figure 13: Ten minute averaged wind speeds at Rosendal for one day in October 2008.

Table 3: Validation of five different transfer functions (wind emulators) and NCEP GFS wind speed versus *in situ* measurements from nine stations. The validation dataset consists of all hours from 2007 and 2008 for which both NCEP and *in situ* wind information is available. <speed> is the mean *in situ* wind speed. “corr” is the correlation between the model or emulator and the *in situ* observations; “bias” is model/emulator wind speed minus *in situ* wind, and “rmse” is the root mean square errors. All wind speeds and bias and rmse are given in m/s.

			NCEP			Emulator 1 (constant bias)			Emulator 2 (bias dependent on model wind direction)			Emulator 3 (bias dependent on model wind direction and speed)			Emulator 4 (bias dependent on model wind speed)			Emulator 5 (Neural network)		
Station	#obs	<speed>	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse
Fedje	2696	7.6	0.88	-0.8	2.2	0.88	-0.9	2.2	0.88	-0.7	2.2	0.81	-0.6	2.5	0.85	-1.1	2.6	0.86	-0.8	2.5
Ona	5493	7.9	0.82	-0.6	2.7	0.82	-1.3	3.0	0.79	-0.8	3.1	0.67	-0.8	3.2	0.74	-2.4	4.2	0.75	-1.4	3.5
Svinøy	5539	8.4	0.82	-1.2	3.0	0.82	-1.4	3.1	0.77	-1.0	3.4	0.75	0.2	3.2	0.79	-2.6	4.2	0.80	-1.3	3.6
Troll	5390	8.0	0.93	0.2	1.6	0.93	0.0	1.6	0.92	0.1	1.8	0.88	-0.1	2.0	0.92	-0.1	1.8	0.93	0.0	1.7
Hasvik	5457	5.6	0.73	1.5	3.0	0.73	1.8	3.2	0.74	1.5	3.0	0.67	1.1	2.7	0.71	3.2	4.2	0.72	1.7	3.0
Fruholmen	5294	8.4	0.84	-0.6	2.6	0.84	-0.8	2.6	0.78	-0.5	2.9	0.74	-0.3	3.0	0.83	-0.3	2.5	0.82	-0.6	2.7
Slettnes	5514	6.9	0.78	0.7	2.6	0.78	0.5	2.6	0.70	0.9	3.2	0.62	1.2	3.5	0.60	-0.3	3.1	0.70	0.8	3.0
Nordkyn	809	6.5	0.81	1.7	2.7	0.81	1.9	2.9	0.74	2.1	3.5	0.67	1.9	3.2	0.70	2.7	3.4	0.80	1.6	2.7
Rosendal	2822	2.8	0.68	1.2	2.3	0.68	0.7	2.1	0.65	0.9	2.4	0.37	0.8	2.4	0.60	1.5	2.5	0.55	0.6	2.2
Overall	39014	6.9	0.81	0.2	2.5	0.81	0.1	2.6	0.77	0.3	2.8	0.69	0.4	2.9	0.75	0.1	3.2	0.77	0.1	2.8

Table 4: Same as Table 3, but the emulators are trained to relate the NCEP GFS winds directly to the *in situ* measurements, instead of to the SAR wind speed.

			NCEP			Emulator 1 (constant bias)			Emulator 2 (bias dependent on model wind direction)			Emulator 3 (bias dependent on model wind direction and speed)			Emulator 4 (bias dependent on model wind speed)			Emulator 5 (Neural network)		
Station	#obs	<speed >	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse	corr	bias	rmse
Fedje	2696	7.6	0.88	-0.8	2.2	0.88	0.1	2.0	0.86	0.1	2.2	0.79	-0.2	2.5	0.88	-0.1	2.0	0.87	-0.1	2.1
Ona	5493	7.9	0.82	-0.6	2.7	0.82	-0.2	2.7	0.81	0.2	2.9	0.73	0.4	3.1	0.74	-2.4	4.2	0.70	-0.5	3.4
Svinøy	5539	8.4	0.82	-1.2	3.0	0.82	-0.1	2.8	0.79	0.3	3.0	0.75	0.2	3.2	0.76	-3.1	4.7	0.75	0.2	3.3
Troll	5390	8.0	0.93	0.2	1.6	0.93	0.0	1.6	0.93	0.1	1.7	0.90	-0.2	1.8	0.93	0.3	1.6	0.93	0.1	1.6
Hasvik	5457	5.6	0.73	1.5	3.0	0.73	0.5	2.7	0.76	0.5	2.6	0.68	0.0	2.5	0.70	1.3	2.9	0.72	0.5	2.6
Fruholmen	5294	8.4	0.84	-0.6	2.6	0.84	0.1	2.5	0.79	0.3	2.8	0.77	0.5	3.0	0.82	-0.4	2.6	0.81	0.2	2.7
Slettnes	5514	6.9	0.78	0.7	2.6	0.78	0.2	2.6	0.73	0.5	2.9	0.69	0.6	2.9	0.73	-1.7	3.1	0.69	0.5	3.0
Nordkyn	809	6.5	0.81	1.7	2.7	0.81	0.4	2.2	0.67	-0.2	3.4	0.67	0.8	2.3	0.69	1.0	1.9	0.79	0.6	1.9
Rosendal	2822	2.8	0.68	1.2	2.3	0.68	-0.1	2.0	0.66	0.1	2.1	0.49	-0.2	2.0	0.63	0.0	1.9	0.68	0.1	1.9
Overall	39014	6.9	0.81	0.2	2.5	0.81	0.1	2.3	0.78	0.2	2.6	0.72	0.2	2.6	0.76	-0.1	2.8	0.77	0.2	2.5

Number of SAR scenes needed to make a robust wind emulator

An important question to address is how many SAR scenes are necessary to develop a robust wind emulator. As discussed in the previous section, the number of scenes available for this study (see Figure 4) seems to be insufficient to properly account for the variation of wind speed (bias) with model wind direction and/or wind speed, at least with the methods tested here. One simple way to get an idea of the number of scenes necessary, is to look at the mean SAR wind speed (or bias versus model wind speed) as a function of the number of scenes used for the averaging. This is shown in Figure 14 for each of the nine stations used for validation.

Figure 14: Average wind speed bias (SAR minus NCEP) plotted versus the number of scenes used for the averaging, for the 9 stations shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. The number of scenes on the x-axis is essentially a timeline from May 2005 to May 2009, except for the buoys Nordkyn and Rosendal where data are available for shorter periods starting in 2007/8.

For most of the stations, the bias seems to be fairly stable after about 200 scenes, although a trend is observed after this for some of the stations.

When the bias is calculated separately for various model wind directions and/or speeds, the number of scenes available for averaging within each bin will be much less. The dependency of the bias on the number of SAR scenes for 12 different angular bins of model wind direction is shown on Figure 15, for the location at Fedje. For several of the wind directions less than 50 scenes are available, and the bias seems not to have reached a stable value. For two of the northerly wind directions (NCEP wind direction between 0-30 degrees and 330-360 degrees)

more than 80 scenes are available. Here the bias seems to have stabilized after about 50 scenes, with a variation less than 0.2 m/s after adding more scenes. Apparently fewer scenes are needed to get a stable bias when wind direction is limited to a certain direction than for overall wind directions, as shown on Figure 14. This seems reasonable, as the restriction on the wind direction should also restrict the variability of the wind speed. To have at least 50 scenes for any 30 degree wind direction bin, a minimum of 600 scenes is necessary. However, at any location certain wind directions are more frequent than others, so a minimum of about 1000 scenes seems to be necessary to develop a robust wind emulator of the type tested in this study. This is achievable with Envisat ASAR alone on higher latitudes, if the complete archive of data would be available. More sophisticated statistical methods could however reduce the number of scenes needed.

Figure 15: Average wind speed bias (SAR minus NCEP) for the location at Fedje plotted versus the number of scenes used for the averaging, for 12 different angular bins of the NCEP wind direction (see Figure 11).

Diurnal wind variations

Sun-synchronous satellites, such as Envisat, cover certain areas of the earth at nearly the same (local solar) time every day. Thus for parameters which may have a systematic diurnal variation, such as wind, climatologies based on satellite measurements may be biased. The study areas of this report are monitored by Envisat around 9 UTC for descending pass and around 21 UTC for ascending pass, with variation of +/- 30 minutes since each point is observed from different orbits at different incidence angles. The average diurnal variation of observed wind speeds for some of the in situ stations is seen in Figure 16. As expected, very

little diurnal variation (< 0.1 m/s) is found for the only offshore station (Troll), but close to the coast the wind speed is higher in the afternoon for the two stations in the Northwest coast of Southern Norway (Ona and Svinøy) and slightly higher before noon for two of the stations in Northern Norway (Hasvik and Fruholmen). The amplitudes of the variation are moderate, below 0.5 m/s, except for Svinøy where the variation is as much as 0.8 m/s.

Figure 16: Mean observed wind as a function of Universal Time for some of the in situ observing stations used in this study. The approximate coverage times of Envisat for ascending and descending paths are indicated with the two vertical lines.

In this study, only model and in situ wind speeds closest in time to the satellite observations are used for the emulator, so there should be no bias in this intercomparison. However, the representativeness of the time-sampled wind estimates should be kept in mind. Since the diurnal variation of wind speed might be linked to variations in stability and/or wind direction, the diurnal variation could be implicitly accounted for by a wind emulator which takes stability and wind direction as input. Sentinel-1, with planned launch in 2011, will have an equator crossing time about 4 hours earlier than Envisat, and will hence provide a different sampling. This should be kept in mind when comparing the two datasets, but complementary sampling of various satellites could be useful to resolve the diurnal variations, if intercalibration is precise enough.

Summary and conclusion

Mean wind speed maps based on Envisat ASAR have been calculated for two Norwegian coastal regions with complex fjord topography, where the wind direction for the SAR wind inversion has been taken from the global NCEP GFS model system. Mean wind speed has also been calculated separately for different model wind directions, and a strong dependency

of the spatial variability of the SAR wind speed on the lower resolution model wind direction is found. This suggests that the SAR composite wind contains useful information that may be used to add spatial detail to lower resolution operational numerical weather forecasts.

A first attempt has been made to parameterise the detailed SAR wind speed variations from the low resolution wind speed and direction available from the model. Two types of such transfer functions (wind emulators) are tested: one based on a neural network, and a simpler approach consisting of determining a bias (SAR minus NCEP wind speed) from a training dataset, with the idea to correct for this bias in the real time situation when SAR wind is not generally available. For the latter type of wind emulator, the bias is determined for the overall case (constant for each pixel), and is also calculated separately for model wind speed and direction within defined discrete bins.

Validation against *in situ* wind measurements on an independent dataset shows however that the accuracy of the NCEP model is not improved by the high resolution transfer functions. An additional exercise where the emulators are trained to predict directly the *in situ* measurements suggests that the accuracy of the *in situ* wind measurements stations is not good enough to validate the moderate spatial wind speed gradients (typically less than 2 m/s), observed with SAR, whereas most of the root mean square errors can be attributed to temporal variability (“randomness”) of the wind in complex terrain, and the lowest possible achievable rmse is estimated to be of the order of 1.6 to 2 m/s for offshore and coastal stations respectively.

The high spatial coherence of the mean SAR wind speed maps (Figure 8 and Figure 9) strengthens the belief that the SAR is able to provide very accurate quantitative description of high resolution spatial wind speed variations. A validation campaign with intercalibrated buoys is suggested to be able to confirm this quantitatively. The spatial coherence is however less for SAR wind speed averages made separately for different model wind directions (Figure 10 and Figure 11) and/or speeds, and it is estimated that a minimum of 1000 SAR images are needed to develop a robust SAR wind emulator.

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